

The ESSENCE Survey 15 Years Later

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In three successive months of 2004, I finished my dissertation, got married, and went down to Chile for my first observing run with the ESSENCE project. I had spent my graduate career at the University of California, Berkeley, under the guidance of Saul Perlmutter and George Smoot. I joined the Supernova Cosmology Project in the spring of 1999, just after the first papers reporting on the discovery of dark energy with Type Ia supernovae (SNeIa) had come out. To take the next steps in SN Ia cosmology, it was clearly time to build on the 18 low-redshift SNeIa from the Calán/Tololo Supernova Survey, the 42 high-redshift supernovae from the Supernova Cosmology Project and 16 nearby SNeIa from the Center for Astrophysics (CfA) sample, and the 10 high-redshift from High-z Supernova Team.

I spent my graduate career developing the supernova search pipeline for the Nearby Supernova Factory to grow and improve the nearby SN Ia sample. In the last years of my graduate career, two groups assembled to build and improve samples of higher-redshift SNeIa. One group would use the 3.6m Canada France Hawaii Telescope (CFHT), and the other the 4m NOAO CTIO Blanco telescope through the NOAO survey program. This was the era where useful, largely contiguous, cosmetically clean mosaic CCD arrays had just become available on 4m-class telescopes, with Mosaic-II on

CTIO and MegaCam on CFHT. Each telescope+instrument was designed for large surveys, and there were specific efforts to organize such programs to realize the potential of these new technological capabilities. Many of the members of the Supernova Cosmology Project joined the Supernova Legacy Survey (SNLS), while the ESSENCE team, which used NOAO facilities, was largely from the High-z Supernova team. In broad strokes the plans were the same: use 4m-class telescopes with wide-field cameras to take repeated observations of a field, find and monitor supernovae photometrically, and then use 6- to 10m-class telescopes to take spectra to confirm the supernova type and to obtain the redshift.

When I took my postdoc with Christopher Stubbs and the ESSENCE survey, I was switching sides. There was some teasing and joking about that, but it turned out to be great. I ended up knowing essentially all of the people doing supernova cosmology during that decade, and it was great to meet people with different perspectives on supernovae and the history of the earlier investigations.

The ESSENCE survey was paired with the SuperMacho NOAO survey to make effective use of half nights. SuperMACHO was observing the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC; RA 05:20, Dec -70:00) to look for microlensing events due to massive compact bodies in the halo of the Milky Way along the line of sight to the LMC. The ESSENCE survey focused on four large fields at Right Ascensions 23:30, 01:10, 02:10, and 02:30 between Declinations of -10 to 0 degrees, so as to be accessible by telescopes in both the northern and southern hemispheres.

ESSENCE would observe in the first half of the nights through September through January, gradually rolling through the fields, with SuperMACHO using the second half of the nights. Working together, both programs brought sustained remote observing to the Blanco telescope. We would observe from a remote observation booth in La Serena, Chile, at the NOAO compound — this was much more sustainable than being up on the mountain to observe only every 2–3 nights. We ran the image subtraction on a cluster in the computing room on the compound, with a goal of

Figure 1: Delta m vs. w. This figure shows the size of the effect we were trying to observe. Credit: Miknaitis et al. 2007

finishing the image subtractions and scanning for supernovae by the following morning.

For spectroscopy, ESSENCE used Keck I and II, the VLT, Gemini North and South, Magellan Clay and Baade, and the MMT [1]. This was the beginning of queue observing time at Gemini. We found that queue mode worked great, as long as one of our team members (often Isobel Hook) was on the mountain. Part of it was morale and focus, and part of it was to provide detailed information on what we needed for SN cosmology. Most spectroscopic systems were focused on obtaining observations of galaxies and would often explicitly center up on the brightest nearby source to get the center of the galaxy. But for supernova observations, we instead needed the offset location of the supernova and required exact knowledge of where the slit was placed,

More broadly, this was a case where having the observing and scientific staff of observatories as active members of science projects yielded better results than more independent teams. And I found it beneficial to have both experts who used the instruments every day and people super-focused on getting the best science. Weekly soccer games with the observatory staff and the inter-observatory olympics were helpful for building teamwork and camaraderie.

The ESSENCE survey was focused on getting two bands, R and I, for 200 SNeIa in a redshift range from $0.2 < z < 0.8$. At the start of the survey it really wasn't clear whether w , the dark energy equation of state parameter, was truly constant with redshift. I certainly was pretty interested in that question when I started the postdoc. I (unfortunately?) remain interested in the question — but in the present day we're looking for little things and small changes in the equation of state over cosmological time. At the time of the ESSENCE survey we didn't know that, and I think that many of us thought we might actually find something measurably different than $w=-1$.

Our major first papers [2, 3] were based on 60 SNeIa from the first part of the survey. These first results from SNLS and ESSENCE introduced detailed systematic error tables, as the field started focusing on the limitations of combining large

numbers of supernovae from different surveys and at different redshifts. Since then the evidence overwhelmingly points to something very well approximated by a constant $w=-1$ model. But the mystery of dark energy remains. As we look forward to an explosion in numbers from the Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time, which should find, during the life of survey, at least 100,000 well-studied SNeIa, and the Nancy Grace Roman Observatory, which will take us securely out to redshifts of ~ 1.5 , the field of supernova cosmology continues to be rich with excitement and potential.

Figure 2: Cosmology OM vs. OL. This figure presents the first ESSENCE+SNLS constraints. The SNLS constraints had been published prior to the SNLS results. Credit: Wood-Vasey et al. 2007

References

- [1] Foley, R. et al., 2008, AJ, 137, 3731. doi:10.1088/0004-6256/137/4/3731
- [2] Miknaitis, G. et al. 2007, ApJ, 666, 674. doi:10.1086/519986
- [3] Wood-Vasey, M. et al. 2007. doi:10.1086/518642